

From En-Route to Touchdown: Uncertainty Analysis of Inbound Traffic Flows to Singapore Changi Airport

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Abstract—Long-Range Air Traffic Flow Management (LR-ATFM) aims to facilitate global, seamless, and efficient traffic coordination by extending traffic flow management to long-haul flights. Accordingly, an integrated optimal solution can be devised to manage inbound traffic, minimizing delays and congestion at the airport and its surrounding airspace. Existing strategies typically separate en-route flight management from tactical measures applied during the descent phase. This study contributes to bridging these two operational phases by analyzing traffic patterns and quantifying the uncertainty in flight time between the top of descent and landing at the destination airport. Significant traffic flows and typical flight times are extracted from historical trajectory data of approximately 135,000 inbound flights to Singapore Changi Airport between March 2019 and January 2020. Subsequently, flight time uncertainty is assessed by comparing the standard deviations at different distances around the airport. The results indicate no substantial variation in flight time uncertainty between 170 NM and 50 NM from the airport. This supports a seamless transition from LR-ATFM to arrival management at the top of descent. Furthermore, significant differences in flight distance and time are observed among various traffic flows, which should be accounted for in future optimization efforts, particularly in runway sequencing.

Keywords—Air Traffic Flow Management; Arrival Management; Long Range Flights; Flight Track Data Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) is a well-established concept for balancing demand with capacity constraints at airports and within airspace sectors [1]. The primary objective is to ensure safe operations throughout the flight by planning movements in advance. Additionally, proactive air traffic management can minimize delays, streamline traffic flows, optimize fuel efficiency, lower emissions, and reduce Air Traffic Controllers (ATCos) workload [2, 3]. Flight schedule data is collected to achieve these objectives, and infrastructure demand is assessed. This information is then compared with frequently reported capacity values to identify critical periods where demand exceeds available capacity.

In such cases, Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) measures are implemented to balance demand fluctuations. International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) Doc. 9971

outlines various potential measures, such as modifications to flight routes or assignment of ground delays [4]. Route modifications may include lateral adjustments, such as level capping to restrict step climbs; vertical adjustments, such as re-routing; and/or longitudinal adjustments, such as increasing intervals between consecutive flights. Ground delays, on the other hand, can be managed by adjusting departure times through slot assignments, which define a designated time window for takeoff procedures as part of the Ground Delay Program (GDP).

Since ATFM systems aim to regulate traffic flows, a sufficient proportion of adjustable flights within the infrastructure system is required to realize their benefits. The threshold for effective ATFM implementation varies across the literature, with most studies indicating a minimum participation rate of 70% or higher [5, 6]. For Singapore Changi Airport (WSSS), a case-specific study determined that at least 75% of flights must be manageable for an ATFM system to be efficient [3]. From an ATFM perspective, domestic flights offer the highest level of flexibility in traffic management [5], as they can be adjusted during both the strategic and pre-tactical phases at the departure airport. However, domestic flights alone do not meet the required threshold in smaller countries, particularly in Europe and Southeast Asia. To address this limitation, cross-border ATFM systems have been implemented, integrating multiple countries to increase the share of controllable flights.

The Network Manager, operated by European Organization for the Safety of Air Navigation (EUROCONTROL), is responsible for executing ATFM in Europe [7, 8]. A so-called ATFM slot is assigned during periods of capacity constraints for Instrument Flight Rules (IFR) flights departing from one of the 42 member states or two adjacent countries. This slot defines a 15-minute time window around the flight's Calculated Take Off Time (CTOT). Consequently, the primary strategy is to delay flights on the ground using a GDP. A similar approach, known as the Distributed Multi-Nodal ATFM Network concept, is implemented in the Asia-Pacific (APAC) region [9]. Unlike the European system, slot calculations are not centralized but managed independently by

individual nodes. Each participating country regulates its own traffic while sharing relevant data via a dedicated platform. This enables partner countries to review and adjust their ATFM strategies, fostering a more harmonized and efficient resolution to demand-capacity imbalances.

Another key difference between the two ATFM systems is the scope of included airports. The Distributed Multi-Nodal ATFM Network initially covered only selected airports. As of 2020, the network comprised 26 airports (13 designated as Level 3 ATFM nodes and 13 as Level 2 ATFM nodes), managed by ten different Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) [9]. In 2024, the Republic of Korea joined the consortium, expanding the system’s coverage to more than 80 airports [10].

Previous traffic data indicates that the required 70–75% traffic threshold for an efficient ATFM system at Singapore Changi Airport is not met [11, 12]. To address this, the Long-Range Air Traffic Flow Management (LR-ATFM) concept was introduced in 2017 to increase the number of adjustable flights [13]. Long-haul flights are typically excluded from strategic and pre-tactical ATFM measures, as they are already airborne when ATFM activities are implemented. Consequently, GDP measures, such as issuing take-off slots, are no longer applicable. Instead, the LR-ATFM concept introduces tactical adjustments during the en-route phase, primarily through minor speed modifications.

Fig. 1 illustrates the fundamental principle of the LR-ATFM concept. A long-haul flight is assigned a Target Time Over (TTO) at a predefined position before entering the descent phase. Based on the aircraft’s current position and the estimated remaining flight time to the TTO reference point, a speed adjustment is calculated and communicated either to the aircraft or the airline operations center. These speed adjustments enable the redistribution of long-haul arrivals, shifting them from peak traffic periods at the destination airport to intervals with lower traffic volume.

A. State-of-the-art

ICAO has addressed LR-ATFM in various documents. ICAO’s Manual on Air Traffic Management System Requirements (Doc 9882) [14] provides comprehensive guidance on ATM system requirements, including aspects related to long-range traffic flow management. In 2017, Goodall [15] discussed the concept of LR-ATFM, focusing on its implemen-

tation strategies. Unfortunately, both publications generally delimit the procedure by the end of the cruise flight.

Schultz et al. [16] present a concept of operations targeting LR-ATFM in the Asia-Pacific region. The need for collaboration among various flight information regions and adherence to local regulations is emphasized. The research utilizes aircraft-transmitted positional data and flight plan information to predict arrival flows at Singapore Changi Airport, demonstrating that speed advisories for long-range flights can effectively mitigate periods of excessive demand. However, disturbances in the arrival time due to actual weather are neglected, and aircraft-specific performance envelopes are not considered in the speed adjustment scenarios.

Subsequently, Rosenow et al. [17] examine how controlling the arrival times of long-haul flights under realistic weather conditions can improve traffic flow. It highlights that control measures and their effects on arrival times and fuel consumption are significantly influenced by individual flight performance and unpredictable weather conditions.

Rosenow et al. [18] examine the challenges and strategies associated with regulating aircraft arrival times, particularly for long-haul flights, in the context of variable weather conditions. By analyzing over 5,000 realistic arrival scenarios for 23 long-haul flights destined for Singapore Changi Airport during peak hours, variables such as speed, route, and the timing of these adjustments across different weather scenarios were varied. The findings suggest that implementing speed or route control measures approximately four hours before arrival is optimal. Beyond five hours, weather-induced uncertainties often outweigh the benefits of such adjustments. Therefore, extended control measures are advisable only under stable weather conditions. The study highlights the critical balance between proactive arrival time management and the unpredictable nature of the weather, providing valuable insights for air traffic management and airline operations.

Shepherd [19] elaborates on traditional ATFM techniques, such as Miles-In-Trail (MIT) and GDPs, which often operate independently and may disproportionately affect certain flights in the Australian airspace. Shepherd introduces the concept of LR-ATFM to distribute delays more equitably among flights, including short-haul and long-haul operations. Drawing from operational initiatives like AEROTHAI’s Bay of Bengal Cooperative ATFM System and NATS’ Extended Arrival Management, Shepherd treats LR-ATFM as the integration of ATFM solutions to collaboratively balance the flow of aircraft to specific air traffic management resources. He states that implementing LR-ATFM requires agreed-upon standards, accurate trajectory predictions, and reliable data exchange, often necessitating collaboration across multiple ANSPs. Civil Air Navigation Services Organisations (CANSOs) white paper on LR-ATFM, [20] delves deeper into operational aspects of LR-ATFM, offering implementation recommendations and models compatible with existing regional ATFM operations. Both CANSO publications do not focus on the uncertainty in arrival time and fuel burn arising from unpredictable weather scenarios. Furthermore, the additional requirements of the Arrival Manager (AMAN) for safe and efficient runway use are not addressed.

Figure 1: LR-ATFM concept based on the ICAO concept trial performed in 2017 [13].

Higasa et al. [21] already pointed out that managing aircraft arrival times in the en-route airspace helps alleviate congestion in the terminal airspace. Therefore, they developed a mathematical model and validated inter-arrival time control to effectively manage upstream traffic flows in en-route airspace. By optimizing traffic flow, the study demonstrated the potential to significantly reduce delay times in both en-route and terminal airspace, supporting the development of an Extended Arrival Manager (E-AMAN) to improve air traffic management systems. However, the question of the most efficient extension of the AMAN radius is not discussed in detail.

Ahrenhold et al. [22] explore a novel coordination process between aircraft Flight Management System (FMS) and Arrival Managers AMAN to facilitate fuel-efficient and sustainable approach procedures. The study extends the traditional scheduling horizon from 50 to 125 nautical miles, allowing for more optimized trajectory planning. A redesigned airspace structure and enhanced controller systems were implemented to support this concept. Human-in-the-loop simulations at Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) Air Traffic Validation Center demonstrated the feasibility of the new airspace design, resulting in reduced flown distances and potential decreases in fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. The study also assessed the workload of ATCos, situational awareness, and perceived safety, finding that the new procedures were manageable within current operational parameters.

Sekine et al. [23] design a feasible En-Route AMAN system with airline-oriented runway assignment rules to minimize taxi times and speed control rules based on inter-aircraft spacing using simulation-based optimization. A decision tree analysis visualizes distinct strategies for traffic control. An agent-based simulation at Tokyo International Airport evaluates system effectiveness, showing significant reductions in arrival delays and taxi times. The study proposes a scientific system design for En-Route AMAN to assist ATCos in runway flow and inter-aircraft control. Using simulation-based optimization, it introduces a runway assignment rule that minimizes taxi time and speed control strategies. A simulation at Tokyo International Airport showed a 21% reduction in arrival sequencing delays and a 6.9% decrease in taxi times. The study highlights that operationally feasible rules can reduce congestion while maintaining interpretability and the potential for AMAN implementation.

Kamo et al. [24] elaborate on 4D-trajectory uncertainty leading to airspace congestion, capacity reduction, delays, and challenges in Air Traffic Controls (ATCs) inter-aircraft separation management for arrival sequences. For simultaneously optimizing descent/approach trajectories and associated arrival sequences under uncertain weather forecasts, they introduced a multi-phase Optimal Control (OC)-based robust trajectory optimization problem for descending/approaching aircraft. They employed the ensemble approach to model the effects of weather forecast uncertainty on trajectories and arrival sequences, proving optimized robust trajectories to mitigate the impact of weather forecast uncertainty. This approach aims to minimize fuel burn and operational

cost increases while respecting constraints. Robust arrival sequences further ensure safe inter-aircraft separations despite 4D-trajectory uncertainties.

B. Research question

This raises the question of whether a transition from LR-ATFM to AMAN activities can be smoothly performed at the Top of Descent (TOD) or whether the uncertainty of the remaining flight time is too high to achieve a stable runway sequence. In other words, flights may not have predictable arrival times at this horizon and should, therefore, be subject to AMAN adjustments in a later flight stage.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Foundation

Automatic Dependent Surveillance - Broadcast (ADS-B) is a surveillance technology that allows aircraft to continuously transmit their position, velocity, and other key flight parameters [25]. Using Mode-S transponders, aircraft broadcast this information on the 1,090 MHz SSR Mode-S downlink frequency (ADS-B Out), enabling reception by ground stations and other aircraft equipped with ADS-B. The signal reception range can extend from 400 to 450 km for high-altitude aircraft but is significantly reduced for those flying at lower altitudes or operating on the ground. Aircraft determine their position through satellite navigation (e.g., Global Positioning System (GPS)), inertial navigation systems, and radio navigation aids, transmitting updates approximately once per second. These messages are received by the ground antenna, processed, and made available for the Air Traffic Management (ATM) community. ADS-B data is essential for the aviation system to improve real-time tracking, enhance airspace efficiency, and support predictive analytics for airport and airspace performance [26]. By reducing dependency on traditional radar systems, ADS-B represents a key component of modern air traffic surveillance and future aviation advancements. It should be noted that the availability of ADS-B information highly depends on the ground receiver infrastructure and is therefore limited above abandoned terrain (e.g., deserts or oceans). ADS-B data is provided to the public through various services such as OpenSky Network (opensky-network.org), Flightradar24 (www.flightradar24.com), or FlightAware (flightaware.com).

TABLE I. Characteristics of the used ADS-B dataset.

Name	Description	Data Type	Unit	Example
orig	Four letter ICAO Code of the origin airport	String	-	KJFK
dest	Four letter ICAO Code of the destination airport	String	-	WSSS
ID	Nine digit alphanumeric unique identifier for each flight	Object	-	79G2LQ5I8
lat	Lateral coordinate of the aircraft position	Float	[°]	1.312121
long	Longitudinal position of the aircraft position	Float	[°]	103.961967
alt	Altitude information in 25 ft steps	Integer	[ft]	875
time	UNIX time stamp in seconds from 01.01.1970	Integer	[s]	1552640713

The ADS-B dataset includes information for 153,159 flights operated between March 2019 and January 2020. A total of 18,991 movements were excluded due to incomplete or poor data quality. More than 51 million data points define the remaining flights. Table I presents an example entry of the dataset. The data can be categorized into flight schedule and trajectory information. The resolution of received data varies between flights due to limitations in capturing outgoing ADS-B messages, particularly over oceans in the APAC region. Additionally, not all aircraft are equipped with the necessary technology for ADS-B monitoring. Hence, the numbers do not fully represent the total traffic volume operated during the data period.

B. Data Analysis

In recent LR-ATFM research considering Singapore Changi Airport, the concept envisaged illustrated in Fig. 1 has been implemented [16, 27, 28]. A key factor is the positioning of the so-called TTO reference point, as it marks the end of LR-ATFM activities and the transition to local AMAN. The initial LR-ATFM trial proposed applying the concept within the en-route phase due to the better predictability of positions and overflight times [13]. Furthermore, this phase typically offers more flexibility than the climb/descent phases, as it is less constrained by ATC activities.

The transition from en route to descent phase was analyzed using the altitude profiles of 31,318 flights covering an air distance greater than 2,200 NM between the origin airport and WSSS. By excluding short- and medium-haul flights, the study ensures that only traffic with a well-defined en-route phase is considered. Fig. 2 (top) illustrates steady altitude profiles for all percentiles investigated until the aircraft reaches a remaining air distance of 170 NM to WSSS. After this threshold, the median altitude gradually decreases, followed by the 2.5% percentile. At approximately 100 NM air distance, a continuous decrease across all altitude percentiles becomes evident. In alignment with the initial LR-ATFM concept recommendations, the TTO reference point is set at 170 NM air distance from WSSS. In the following, this refers to the beginning of the arrival sector.

A flight is considered in the arrival sector once it crosses its boundary and remains there until touchdown at WSSS. The time spent within this area is analyzed for approximately 126,000 flights in Fig. 2 (bottom). Flights departing within the sector, known as pop-up flights, are not considered. In the event of an unfavorable approach direction into the sector under consideration of the currently used runway configuration, an extended approach path may result. Since tactical ATFM measures are applied within this area, dwell times can vary significantly. These activities include holding patterns and vectoring between the Air Traffic System (ATS) route waypoints. Both procedures increase the actual flight distance and the time spent within the sector compared to the initially planned trajectory.

On the other hand, direct routing is employed by ATCos to increase flight efficiency and reduce workload [29]. This results in shortcuts and, consequently, a shorter approach

Figure 2: Top: Altitude profile depending on the remaining air distance from long-haul flights to Singapore Changi Airport. Bottom: Histogram of dwell times for all recorded flights.

route than originally conceptualized. These factors collectively contribute to the wide variation in dwell times, as Fig. 2 (bottom) suggests. Previous optimization efforts aimed to balance the traffic volume in the arrival sector by assuming a dwell time of 40:25 minutes (75% quantile) for each flight from sector entry until landing at WSSS. This value was deliberately set as a conservative estimate to prevent underestimation of arrival sector capacity utilization.

Fig. 3 reveals the recorded trajectories with a focus on the Terminal Manoeuvring Area (TMA) surrounding WSSS. The dense blue lines indicate clear main traffic flows approaching the airport from different directions. Surrounding these flows, isolated off-track movements result in blurred blue areas. Within a 50 NM radius, four commonly used holding patterns are identified. The routing variations of the main traffic flows, based on their entry direction into the arrival sector, suggest differences in route efficiency in terms of flown distance.

A conducted LR-ATFM trial recommends actively managing long-haul flights to WSSS at least 4 – 5 hours before reaching the TTO reference point [13]. The traffic situation and demand within the arrival sector is expected to be highly uncertain, as most short- and medium-haul flights arriving at WSSS within the same period as LR-ATFM flights may not yet be airborne or are still at their departure airport. Therefore, a standard approach phase should be assumed when calculating an optimized TTO at the arrival sector boundary and for estimating a landing time at WSSS. A detailed analysis is conducted to refine the previously used assumption of a deterministic dwell time of 40:25 minutes, taking into account entry direction, runway configuration,

Figure 3: Traffic flows to Singapore Changi Airport, focusing on the Terminal Maneuvering Area.

and tactically assigned detours. Subsequently, distributions for standard flight dwell times are generated and analyzed in terms of uncertainty and magnitude of flight distances and durations.

1) *Sector Entry Direction*: As WSSS is an important hub and one of the largest airports in the world in terms of aircraft movements and passengers, the airport is served by flights from all directions of the world [30]. To classify these traffic flows, sections are defined using a Gaussian Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), which aims to separate the main traffic flows. For this purpose, the bearing of each flight's arrival sector entry position relative to WSSS is calculated. The KDE assigns equal weight to each bearing angle, and based on a Gaussian kernel, it generates a distribution of frequently used entry angles. Fig. 4 depicts the resulting curve. To ensure a smooth transition between angular values, each bearing is transformed into its sine and cosine components, maintaining cyclical continuity between 0° and 360°. The section boundaries are determined by identifying all local minima of the Gaussian KDE function. In this analysis, the algorithm identifies ten distinct sections.

Fig. 5 shows the entry positions of nearly 130,000 flights. The intensity of the blue dot clouds represents significant entry traffic flows. Black lines mark the resulting section boundaries. Each section is characterized by a different span of entry bearings, reflecting the distinct routing patterns of incoming flights. Table II provides additional traffic information for each entry section into the arrival sector. More than 50 % of flights approach WSSS from the northwest and north

Figure 4: Definition of sections based on the entry position angle into the arrival sector using Gaussian Kernel Density Estimation.

via sections IX, X, or I. The latter two predominantly use short- and medium-haul traffic from adjacent countries.

In contrast, section IX serves as the primary arrival gate for flights from Europe, the Middle East, and North America (New York). Thus, this sector is assigned the highest number of long-haul flights (7,784), where the origin and destination airports are more than 2,200 NM apart. Sections II to V also accommodate a significant number, with more than 4,000 long-haul movements. Flights originating from Japan or China

Figure 5: Representation of the ten defined sectors based on the Kernel Density Estimation results of arriving traffic 170 NM before reaching Singapore Changi Airport.

TABLE II. Traffic figures for all defined entry sections into the arrival sector.

Section	Orientation	Total flights		Long-haul flights
I	10.5°	27,973	(22.1%)	2,358
II	38.3°	8,225	(6.5%)	4,451
III	75.9°	13,265	(10.5%)	4,172
IV	107.7°	5,140	(4.1%)	4,100
V	132.8°	11,734	(9.3%)	4,095
VI	181.1°	15,210	(12.0%)	1,064
VII	234.6°	572	(0.5%)	535
VIII	263.7°	1,203	(1.0%)	174
IX	298.8°	25,116	(19.8%)	7,784
X	342.2°	18,194	(14.4%)	2,585

arrive predominantly through sections II and III, and inbound traffic from Australia enters the arrival sector primarily via sections IV or V. In conclusion, these sections are the most important ones within the scope of LR-ATFM, since their specific dwell times significantly impact the concept.

2) *Runway configuration in use:* The current runway configuration in use has a significant impact on the flown approach path. Thus, the landing direction is determined for each flight using the recorded heading within the flight track data. Since the data quality of ADS-B data decreases the closer the aircraft is to the ground, the last recorded position before reaching an altitude of 1,000 ft but not higher than 5,000 ft is used as a reference. This approach ensures a balance between accuracy and the availability of flight data. The strategy aims to select a recorded position on or close to the final approach after passing a Final Approach Fix (FAF), where the aircraft is aligned to the runway [31]. However, it is necessary to consider that certain external factors, such as weather conditions or ATC instructions, may lead to deviations from standard approach paths. It should be noted that the logic does not allow an unambiguous detection of the used runway since WSSS operates two parallel runways for civil aviation. Due to data quality reasons, 2,308 flights (around 1.8% of total movements) are sorted out since no ADS-B position was recorded, which fulfills the altitude criterion for determining the landing runway direction. Fig. 6 reveals the trajectory of 24,196 flights entering the arrival sector in section IX between 271.9° and 325.7°. 14,265 (59%) flights are using landing direction 02 via runway threshold 02L or 02C (*north*) and 9,931 (41%) flights approaching via the opposite direction using threshold 20R or 20C (*south*).

Two significant traffic flows can be identified for approaches from the north. One flow (*IX north-a*) is routed above the mainland of Malaysia and north via Singapore. The other one is routed above the water from the Strait of Malacca and Strait of Singapore (*IX north-b*), leading to a sweeping arc before alignment with the runway. Differentiating these two flows is crucial for accurately modeling arrival sector behavior. Fig. 7 shows the histogram of the total flown distance of all section IX flights within the arrival sector divided by the used landing direction. Two significant peaks can be observed for arrivals approaching from the north. The substantial distance deviation between the histogram maxima confirms the indication from Fig. 6. Flow *IX north-a* is routed

Figure 6: Classification of flights arriving from the northwest (Section IX) to Singapore Changi Airport based on the used runway alignment for landing.

more directly to WSSS within the 50 NM cycle, which results in a lower total flown distance for flights guided via this route. Since a longer flown distance leads with a sufficient probability to a longer dwell time in the sector, a separate consideration of the flows is required to increase the robustness of the dwell time distributions.

To achieve this objective, a Gaussian KDE is applied to the flown distances, resulting in the red curve shown in Fig. 7. To statistically validate the observed bimodality, Hartigan's Dip Test is performed to assess whether the sample originates from a uni-modal distribution or exhibits multiple modes [32, 33]. This test quantifies the most significant deviation (dip) between the empirical distribution function and the closest uni-modal distribution. The p-value indicates the likelihood of observing such a deviation under the assumption of unimodality: a low p-value (<0.05) provides evidence for multi-

Figure 7: Histogram of flown distances within the arrival sector depending on the used runway alignment to define homogeneous traffic flows.

Figure 8: Visualization of the identified traffic flows from the arrival sector section IX. Left: Landing direction 02 (*IX south*). Center: Landing direction 20 approaching via north of Singapore (*IX north-a*). Right: Landing direction 20 approaching via south from Singapore (*IX north-b*).

modality, whereas a high p-value accepts uni-modality. For approaches from the north, the p-value is close to zero, strongly suggesting multi-modality. In contrast, Hartigan's Dip Test for the Gaussian KDE curve of arrivals from the south results in a p-value of 0.99, confirming uni-modality. Consequently, the northern approaches are segmented based on the local minimum of the Gaussian KDE curve between the two peaks (see Fig. 8 center and right).

3) *Detour Effects*: In the final step, flight routes heavily influenced by the responsible ATCOs must be extracted to reduce noise from approach trajectories with large detours. As previously mentioned, vectoring and holdings may lead to an extension of the approach route, affecting dwell times in the arrival sector. Fig. 8 (left) depicts a commonly used holding pattern for traffic flow *IX south* in the lower central part of the map and Fig. 7 shows the corresponding total flown distance in the arrival sector for arrivals using runway direction 02 (blue histogram). The distribution resembles a right-skewed normal distribution. Since 170 NM is the minimum air distance from the entry point to WSSS, outliers with exceptionally short flight distances are constrained. Shortcuts and direct routings are either common for most flights or do not significantly impact the total flown distance of a flight. On the other hand, outliers with a considerably greater traveled distance contribute to the right skewness of the distribution.

The definition of outliers is based on the Gaussian KDE peak of flown distances and the standard holding pattern distance, which is defined in ICAO Doc. 8168 - Volume II [31] and is applied for WSSS airport proofed by historical approach charts published in the Aeronautical Information Publication (AIP) for summer 2019 [34]. Usually, multiple options for performing holdings along the Standard Arrival Routes (STARs) are defined. A holding procedure consists of four phases: two straight and two curved segments forming an oval pattern. The segment duration and the maximum permitted speed vary depending on the pattern altitude. The shortest complete standard holding procedure is defined for altitudes below 14,000 ft. In this case, each segment must be flown for one minute at a maximum speed of 230 kt. The speed limit represents an Indicated Airspeed (IAS),

shown to the crew via the flight deck. The conversion of this speed into a ground distance is theoretically achieved using ground speed. However, instrument installation errors, adiabatic compression, altitude correction, and wind influence must be considered. Since the conversion of speeds depends on the aircraft type and the specific flight profile, the impact of these factors is neglected, and 230 kt is assumed to be equal to the ground speed. This results in a theoretical holding pattern ground distance of 15.33 NM.

The maximum ground distance that leads to a classification as a typical flight is determined by adding the ground distance from the Gaussian KDE maximum and an assumed additional tolerance of 15 NM. For traffic flow *IX south*, the distance threshold is approximately 214 NM. All flights exceeding this ground distance in the arrival sector are excluded from the analysis. Fig. 9 demonstrates the approach's applicability. The flight paths marked in red represent the excluded flight routes, which are movements using the holding pattern in the lower middle part of the map. In total, 3,449 flights (approx. 25%) with significant detours are removed from consideration. As a

Figure 9: Illustration of considered (blue) and neglected (red) trajectories separated based on a maximum distance threshold.

Figure 10: Comparison of considered trajectories with the designed Standard Arrival Route (STAR) ARAMA 1A for the arrival flow to runway 02L/C (*IX south*) according to AIP Singapore (effective date: 03-06-2019) [34].

result, 10,227 flights (approx. 75%) remain as representative samples for the common approach case.

To evaluate the robustness of the algorithm, the selected trajectories are compared with the typical STAR procedure used for the aircraft approaches (see Fig. 10). In this context, the STAR ARAMA 1A begins approximately 50 NM around WSSS, starting at the eponymous waypoint ARAMA, where the inbound traffic is merged. The figure suggests the application of tactical ATC measures to improve traffic efficiency, specifically through shortcuts between the waypoints ARAMA and BOKIP. However, given the overall approach sector defined as a 170 NM radius around the airport, this shortcut does not result in a substantially reduced dwell time.

4) *Flight Time Distribution Determination*: After filtering inbound traffic based on entry direction, landing runway configuration, traffic flow separation, and removing flights with significant detours, the remaining flights within each

Figure 11: Determination of traffic flow-specific normal distributions.

Figure 12: Algorithm to generate inbound traffic flow specific normal distributions of the dwell time within the arrival sector.

traffic flow are considered representative and used to generate a distribution of dwell times within the arrival sector. Fig. 11 shows the histogram of dwell times for traffic flow *IX south* (blue). The red-marked values represent dwell times from excluded flights that did not meet the detour criterion. Flights with particularly long dwell times are predominantly excluded, reinforcing the validity of the applied methodology. The selected flight data are fitted to a normal distribution whose parameters are used to analyze the uncertainty. The entire method for inbound traffic analysis related to dwell time in the arrival sector is summarized in Fig. 12 as a flowchart.

III. RESULTS

Table III shows the algorithm's results applied to all defined inbound sections. Only for traffic flow *IX north*, Hartigan's Dip Test identified a significant bimodal distribution, indicated by a p-value lower than 0.05. A tendency toward multi-modal distributions in the flown distance histogram can be observed for a specific landing direction for sections I, IV, and V. This pattern arises from multiple inbound traffic flows within the sector, which converge after a short distance within the section. Thus, separating these traffic flows is not required. The proportion of excluded flights due to exceeding the defined distance criterion ranges between 14 % and 27 %,

TABLE III. Traffic figures and dwell times distributions for identified traffic flows 170 NM around Singapore Changi Airport.

Traffic Flow	Traffic Figures					Dwell Time Distribution [mm:ss]	
	Total flights	Distance limit [NM]	Neglected flights	Avg. distance [NM]		Mean (μ)	Standard deviation (σ)
<i>I south</i>	12,105	229	2,743 (22.7%)	213		37:45	02:44
<i>I north</i>	15,021	198	2,968 (19.8%)	182		32:27	02:13
<i>II south</i>	3,674	229	792 (21.6%)	215		36:59	02:33
<i>II north</i>	4,355	199	725 (16.6%)	184		32:04	02:06
<i>III south</i>	5,963	215	1,405 (23.6%)	201		34:34	02:10
<i>III north</i>	6,620	216	1,063 (16.1%)	201		34:51	02:21
<i>IV south</i>	2,140	208	541 (25.3%)	194		33:17	02:26
<i>IV north</i>	2,551	211	450 (17.6%)	196		34:06	02:28
<i>V south</i>	5,450	209	1,278 (23.4%)	195		33:40	02:21
<i>V north</i>	5,504	212	974 (17.7%)	198		34:25	02:18
<i>VI south</i>	7,198	190	1,816 (25.2%)	177		31:22	01:56
<i>VI north</i>	7,417	219	1,287 (17.4%)	207		37:04	02:11
<i>VII south</i>	291	192	42 (14.4%)	178		31:11	01:53
<i>VII north</i>	242	233	38 (15.7%)	218		38:49	02:45
<i>VIII south</i>	602	199	104 (17.3%)	185		32:21	02:01
<i>VIII north</i>	528	240	78 (14.8%)	225		39:14	02:30
<i>IX south</i>	13,676	214	3,449 (25.2%)	199		34:14	02:24
<i>IX north-a</i>	2,531	208	169 (6.7%)	195		33:27	02:05
<i>IX north-b</i>	6,749	255	1,240 (18.4%)	239		41:49	02:49
<i>X south</i>	8,235	228	2,195 (26.7%)	215		37:53	02:28
<i>X north</i>	9,432	198	2,241 (23.8%)	184		32:46	01:58

except for flow *IX north-a*, where only 6.7% of the flights were excluded.

In general, for flows that are advantageously aligned between the sector entry and landing threshold, a shorter average flown distance can be observed (e.g., *I north*, *II north*, *X north*, *VI south*, or *VII south*). However, if the approach for these flows uses the opposite runway threshold for landing, a significant detour up to 30 NM occurs. This has a direct impact on the dwell time in the sector. The mean values of the normal distributions show a variation of five to seven minutes, indicating a significant extension. Traffic flows entering the arrival sector transversely to the runway system alignment are unaffected by the runway configuration in use. The average flown distance and mean dwell time are nearly equal for both flows from section *III*, *IV*, *V*, or *IX south* compared to *IX north-a*. The comparison of mean values across individual traffic flows reveals substantial heterogeneity, underscoring the need for a more detailed investigation into arrival sector dwell times, as compared to the previously used deterministic assumption. The previously anticipated dwell time of 40:25 minutes is significantly higher than all traffic flow mean values, except for flow *IX north-b*. Hence, previous optimization activities substantially overestimated arrival sector demand. The standard deviation expresses the uncertainty associated with the remaining flight time, which equals around 02:00 to 02:30 minutes in most cases. However, a trend indicating lower standard deviations for flows with shorter mean values can be identified.

In the next step, the radius of the investigated horizon is reduced from 170 NM to 50 NM in 20 NM steps to assess the impact of decreasing flight distance on the dwell time distribution. Fig. 13 depicts the results for traffic flow *IX south*. It should be noted that only flights considered in the initial case, considering a distance of 170 NM, are

analyzed to enable better comparability of the parameters. The mean values decrease by around four minutes with each successive reduction in horizon size. However, between 70 and 50 NM, the difference increases due to a change in flight direction before reaching the 50 NM horizon, which results in a longer dwell time in this circle segment (see Fig. 8 (left)). The standard deviation decreases slightly by 20 seconds between the 170 NM and the 50 NM horizon, which does not significantly improve the arrival time prediction accuracy.

The standard deviation, in particular, is a key factor for assessing the uncertainty of arrival times. Table IV illustrates these values for all considered horizons and traffic flows. The percentage change always refers to the 170 NM horizon. Between 170 NM and 110 NM, only a marginal change

Figure 13: Histogram and normal distribution of dwell times for different horizon radii around Singapore Changi airport.

TABLE IV. Dwell time standard deviation under decreasing horizon radii until reaching Singapore Changi airport. The delta value references the initial standard deviation for the beginning of the arrival sector at 170 NM.

Traffic Flow	Standard deviation (σ) [mm:ss]												
	170 NM	150 NM		130 NM		110 NM		90 NM		70 NM		50 NM	
<i>I south</i>	02:44	02:42	(-1.2%)	02:39	(-3.0%)	02:35	(-5.5%)	02:30	(-8.5%)	02:21	(-14.0%)	02:12	(-19.5%)
<i>I north</i>	02:13	02:11	(-1.5%)	02:07	(-4.5%)	02:03	(-7.5%)	01:57	(-12.0%)	01:47	(-19.5%)	01:34	(-29.3%)
<i>II south</i>	02:33	02:32	(-0.7%)	02:30	(-2.0%)	02:27	(-3.9%)	02:20	(-8.5%)	02:11	(-14.4%)	02:01	(-20.9%)
<i>II north</i>	02:06	02:04	(-1.6%)	02:02	(-3.2%)	01:58	(-6.3%)	01:52	(-11.1%)	01:43	(-18.3%)	01:30	(-28.6%)
<i>III south</i>	02:10	02:09	(-0.8%)	02:07	(-2.3%)	02:05	(-3.8%)	02:02	(-6.2%)	01:57	(-10.0%)	01:49	(-16.2%)
<i>III north</i>	02:21	02:20	(-0.7%)	02:19	(-1.4%)	02:19	(-1.4%)	02:16	(-3.5%)	02:12	(-6.4%)	02:03	(-12.8%)
<i>IV south</i>	02:26	02:25	(-0.7%)	02:23	(-2.1%)	02:20	(-4.1%)	02:16	(-6.8%)	02:08	(-12.3%)	01:57	(-19.9%)
<i>IV north</i>	02:28	02:26	(-1.4%)	02:25	(-2.0%)	02:23	(-3.4%)	02:19	(-6.1%)	02:12	(-10.8%)	02:01	(-18.2%)
<i>V south</i>	02:21	02:19	(-1.4%)	02:18	(-2.1%)	02:15	(-4.3%)	02:12	(-6.4%)	02:06	(-10.6%)	01:56	(-17.7%)
<i>V north</i>	02:18	02:17	(-0.7%)	02:15	(-2.2%)	02:13	(-3.6%)	02:10	(-5.8%)	02:05	(-9.4%)	01:56	(-15.9%)
<i>VI south</i>	01:56	01:56	(-0.0%)	01:55	(-0.9%)	01:54	(-1.7%)	01:52	(-3.4%)	01:49	(-6.0%)	01:38	(-15.5%)
<i>VI north</i>	02:11	02:10	(-0.8%)	02:10	(-0.8%)	02:09	(-1.5%)	02:08	(-2.3%)	02:06	(-3.8%)	02:00	(-8.4%)
<i>VII south</i>	01:53	01:52	(-0.9%)	01:51	(-1.8%)	01:51	(-1.8%)	01:49	(-3.5%)	01:45	(-7.1%)	01:37	(-14.2%)
<i>VII north</i>	02:45	02:43	(-1.2%)	02:41	(-2.4%)	02:40	(-3.0%)	02:39	(-3.6%)	02:37	(-4.8%)	02:34	(-6.7%)
<i>VIII south</i>	02:01	01:59	(-1.7%)	01:58	(-2.5%)	01:56	(-4.1%)	01:56	(-4.1%)	01:52	(-7.4%)	01:43	(-14.9%)
<i>VIII north</i>	02:30	02:28	(-1.3%)	02:25	(-3.3%)	02:24	(-4.0%)	02:23	(-4.7%)	02:20	(-6.7%)	02:16	(-9.3%)
<i>IX south</i>	02:24	02:16	(-5.6%)	02:13	(-7.6%)	02:10	(-9.7%)	02:09	(-10.4%)	02:08	(-11.1%)	02:04	(-13.9%)
<i>IX north-a</i>	02:05	01:56	(-7.2%)	01:53	(-9.6%)	01:50	(-12.0%)	01:48	(-13.6%)	01:46	(-15.2%)	01:43	(-17.6%)
<i>IX north-b</i>	02:49	02:42	(-4.1%)	02:41	(-4.7%)	02:40	(-5.3%)	02:40	(-5.3%)	02:40	(-5.3%)	02:39	(-5.9%)
<i>X south</i>	02:28	02:28	(-0.0%)	02:27	(-0.7%)	02:27	(-0.7%)	02:21	(-4.7%)	02:13	(-10.1%)	02:05	(-15.5%)
<i>X north</i>	01:58	01:58	(-0.0%)	01:57	(-0.8%)	01:56	(-1.7%)	01:51	(-5.9%)	01:42	(-13.6%)	01:30	(-23.7%)

in standard deviation is observed. Subsequently, many flows experience a significant leap, which does not necessarily indicate an improvement in predictability. The maximum standard deviation reduction is 39 seconds for traffic flow *I north*. Thus, the primary uncertainty source occurs within the 50 NM horizon, depending on the turning position onto the final approach. Therefore, the assumption of the 170 NM horizon as the reference point for LR-ATFM and as the starting position for estimating the landing time is justified, as the uncertainty only decreases significantly shortly before landing.

While the primary focus of this study lies in the retrospective analysis of inbound flight trajectories, the presented methodology provides a data-driven basis for advancing future concepts in arrival traffic management. Managing uncertainty during the descent phase is essential in the context of LR-ATFM, particularly when issuing early speed advisories to long-haul flights to meet the TTO at the reference point. Given that such decisions are typically made 5–6 hours before arrival, the ability to anticipate and model uncertainty in arrival time prediction becomes critical. The results offer a practical basis for enhancing long-range traffic planning with uncertainty-aware adjustments, enabling more efficient and coordinated inbound traffic management. This allows a more strategic use of runway capacity and supports a harmonized planning process between long-range traffic flow management and local arrival sequencing systems.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the scope of Long-Range Air Traffic Flow Management (LR-ATFM), minor speed adjustments are assigned to long-haul flights to include them in inbound flow management activities. However, the concept manages the flights only until reaching a reference point in the en-route phase. This paper analyzes the subsequent descent phase, which includes

tactical arrival flow management activities, such as holding or vectoring. Predicting the estimated landing time to synchronize these local actions with LR-ATFM is essential for enhancing the robustness of long-haul flight adjustments. Thus, the gap between the reference point and touchdown at the destination airport must be closed.

Historical flight track data of approaching traffic to Singapore Changi Airport (WSSS) between March 2019 and January 2020 is analyzed to achieve this objective. The study focuses on dwell time within sectors defined by fixed radii ranging from 170 NM to 50 NM around the airport. First, entry sections are defined based on the bearing of flights relative to WSSS using Gaussian Kernel Density Estimation (KDE). Subsequently, traffic flows are described, and flow-specific filtering steps are applied to extract flights affected by tactical measures that extend flight distance. The remaining flights are used to form traffic flow-specific dwell time normal distributions. These distributions are then examined to assess flight time uncertainty and evaluate the accuracy of landing time predictions.

The results reveal a significant influence of entry direction into the arrival sector on the remaining flight time until landing at WSSS. This is primarily caused by variations in the efficiency and directness of the designed approach routes. The uncertainty, quantified by the standard deviation of dwell times across all traffic flows, decreases with a shorter horizon around WSSS but does not substantially improve compared to the initially defined reference radius of 170 NM. This finding supports using the previously defined LR-ATFM reference radius as the starting point for calculating estimated landing times.

It should be noted that this study analyzed historical flight data, which is inherently affected by Air Traffic Control (ATC) interventions and, therefore, not entirely unimpeded. Various methods were applied to group comparable trajectory

ries into traffic flows and to exclude flights with significant detours, thereby minimizing the influence of outliers on the generated normal distributions. However, actual flight operations are subject to interactions with other aircraft and external factors, such as wind effects. As a result, the computed distributions reflect these operational influences, which impact both their accuracy and overall shape.

The resulting dwell time distributions represent another crucial step toward incorporating long-haul flights into the management of inbound traffic. In subsequent research, the prediction of estimated landing times for long-haul flights could be enhanced by integrating the findings of this study with previous LR-ATFM research, which primarily focused on the en-route phase. This integration would facilitate the inclusion of long-haul flights in the arrival manager's sequencing activities, offering opportunities to optimize inbound traffic efficiency and achieve both delay reduction and fuel savings through the early management of inbound traffic flows.

The proposed methodology relies exclusively on ADS-B flight trajectory data and publicly available airport information, such as runway alignments and reference coordinates provided in the respective Aeronautical Information Publication (AIP). This data-driven design ensures independence from airport-specific custom adjustments or configurations. Consequently, given the availability of analogous input data, the approach is theoretically transferable to other airports or related operational scenarios. This underlines its potential for broader applicability, particularly in environments with available standardized and open-source data.

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